

Relativistic rotating dust-like sphere of infinitesimal mass

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Annotation

This paper presents a relativistic model of a rotating dust sphere in the absence of density and gravity. Geometric deformation is determined solely by kinematics within the framework of special relativity. The calculations are based on the author's method for calculating a relativistic dust disk of infinitesimal mass. The analytical expression for the deformation and shape of the sphere is determined as a function of the radius, polar angle, and angular velocity.

Keywords: Special relativity, dust sphere, relativistic rotation.

1. Geometry of deformation

In [11], it was possible to derive a formula for the deformation of a massless disk, which shows the geometry of the deformed metric:

$$z(x) = -\frac{\sqrt{3}c}{2\omega} \ln\left(1 - \frac{\omega^2 x^2}{c^2}\right) \quad (1)$$

At $c=1$

$$z(x) = -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\omega} \ln(1 - \omega^2 x^2) \quad (2)$$

Obviously, the function $z(x)$ does not provide Einstein's vacuum solution and does not claim to be an independent metric. It is used as a geometric embedding of a spatial section of a stationary rotating Gödel-type system, given the availability of a reliable coordinate system for Z .

To determine the deformation of a sphere, it is necessary to divide it into infinitely thin disks with a thickness of dz parallel to the XY plane.

Coordinates of the center of the disk on the Z axis:

$$z_{\theta} = r \cos(\theta)$$

Coordinates of the edge of the cut disc on the X axis:

$$x_{\theta} = r \sin(\theta)$$

Here, r is the radius of the sphere before rotation.

θ is the polar angle.

Consequently,

$$z(r, \theta) = r \cos \theta - \frac{\sqrt{3} c}{2\omega} \ln \left(1 - \frac{r^2 \sin^2(\theta) \omega^2}{c^2} \right) \quad (3)$$

At $c=1$

$$z(r, \theta) = r \cos \theta - \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2\omega} \ln(1 - r^2 \sin^2(\theta) \omega^2) \quad (4)$$

Note that $c/\omega = R$ is the radius of the light cylinder, which is the critical boundary of the sphere. If we take $R=1$, we get convenient analytical formulas for creating geometric shapes in 3D:

For the disc:

$$z(x) = -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \ln(1 - x^2) \quad (5)$$

For the sphere:

$$z(r, \theta) = r \cos \theta - \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \ln(1 - r^2 \sin^2(\theta)) \quad (6)$$

In (5) and (6), the parameters x and r are defined as fractions of the radius of the light cylinder, taken to be equal to 1, $R = 1$. The figure shows how the shape of the disk changes as it approaches the boundary of the light cylinder.

As can be seen from the figure, as the sphere rotates, it is deformed in the direction of the rotation axis. This deformation depends sharply on the radius of the sphere and increases as the radius approaches the radius of the light cylinder, and therefore also depends on ω and θ .

2. Discussion

Asymmetric bulging and strong dependence on angular velocity in the absence of a gravitational source make it possible to speak of purely kinematic deformations of the metric.

It should be expected that the tangential velocity vector acquires additional distortion due to changes in geometry along the perpendicular direction. Therefore, motion of the metric itself is observed in the direction of the rotation axis, the Z axis. The motion of any material object within this moving geometry cannot but influence its trajectory. In such an anisotropic, dynamic metric, nonequivalent flows of time may be observed along different directions.

3. Geometric redistributions

Based on analytical expressions for perimeters, an important regularity can be traced: with an increase in angular velocity ω , the equatorial perimeter PXY decreases while the vertical PZX perimeter increases.

This behavior indicates a redistribution of the metric's geometry: contraction along one direction is partially or completely compensated for by expansion in the other. The law of conservation in the classical sense does not manifest itself here, but in geometric terms it can resemble an anisotropic extension of a metric.

For the central observer (located in the center of the sphere), such a violation of the uniformity of the metric motion is equivalent to a localized expansion of a rotating system along a certain direction.

4. The Possibility of Observing Anisotropy in Cosmology

As a hypothesis: a directed change in the metric in the presence of rotation leads to an uneven distribution of the density of matter in orthogonal directions even without taking into account force fields of different nature.

figures

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